

LEGAL RESPONSIBILITY IN PUBLIC RELATIONS COPYWRITING

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Abstract

In this article we have mentioned some of the rules that are required in public relations work, insisting on the application of ethics in writing copy in this field.

Our aim is to demonstrate that writing public relations copy is not just about presenting situations in a biased way, but rather about putting together messages that can be tailored to both specific media types and audiences, the copywriter having the obligation to know these issues in detail.

Keywords: responsibility, public relations, copywriter, messages, writing.

Introduction

The communicator needs to know when to communicate and what to communicate through a message, which involves not only the action of communicating, and even before it, but also, analysis, discernment and, last but not least, planning¹.

As the job market is in a state of constant transformation and change, the copywriter is simultaneously being asked to do certain things that used to represent well-established categories belonging to a diverse range of professions. Thus, some public relations people refuse to write advertising copy, not realising that they may at some point end up in a job that requires this skill².

A good number of people working in public relations jobs are trying hard to learn how to make web pages, while others leave this task to a graphic designer who, if he or she is not efficient in writing copy, will not produce good results. For this reason, it is necessary for a copywriter to be versatile, in other words, to adapt to the requirements of the various types of media by applying as effectively as possible both the visual and the aural elements included in the correct transmission of the message.

¹ Cf. Matei-Săvulescu, Aura, Cristina Munteanu, *Etică și deontologie în mass-media și relații publice*, Pitești: Editura Independența Economică, 2004, page 67

² Cf. Viorica Păuș, *Comunicare și resurse umane*, Ed. Polirom, Iași, 2006, pages 76-79

We can therefore say that the emphasis is beginning to fall on responsibility and on proving that written messages achieve their purpose, which is why those copywriters who have skills in obtaining information, understanding it and conveying it accurately will be much more highly rated. There is, however, a difference between writing public relations copy and writing literary, news and advertising copy, and this needs to be understood. The difference between literary copywriting and public relations copywriting is the power and responsibility that the copywriter also has from a legal point of view.

Public relations copywriters write material for all types of media that can convey information, and more often than not these messages - words, images and sounds - are transmitted electronically. In theory, these messages can be received anywhere in the world³.

The responsibility of the copywriters therefore involves two aspects, one relating to how an organisation's actions and policy can affect people, and here we refer to the direct interaction of employees with customers, and the other relating to the fact that good policy and good actions are of little value as long as people do not understand that policy and are not informed about those actions.

Freedom of opinion. Rules limiting freedom of expression

It is well known that freedom of opinion and expression is a fundamental right of every human being and is closely linked to the right of access to information, so this right also applies to the copywriters in the field of public relations. Freedom of expression was included in the preamble to the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights* as one of the four fundamental freedoms at the General Assembly on 10 December 1948 and states: *human beings shall enjoy freedom of speech and belief and shall be free from fear and want*. Article 19 states *that everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference by outsiders and freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers of state*⁴.

This *Universal Declaration* must be respected by all pawns on the human stage, representing an obligation applied in every state as part of international law. The press therefore has the right to free expression, but also has certain legal duties and responsibilities regarding the messages it conveys to the public. The Romanian Government has the duty to provide and guarantee in this context the aforementioned right to all persons on Romanian territory.

There are, of course, several restrictions regarding this right, the purpose of which is to ensure recognition and respect of the rights and freedoms of others and to satisfy the moral

³ Ibidem, page 82

⁴ Matei-Săvulescu, Aura, Cristina Munteanu, *Etică și deontologie în mass-media și relații publice*, Pitești: Editura Independența Economică, 2004, page 89

requirements of public opinion in a democratic state. The Romanian State is a party to this Covenant, which means that the Romanian Government has a legal obligation to comply fully with the provisions of the *Universal Covenant* adopted on 16 December 1966.

However, freedom of expression and information of the press may be restricted in accordance with Article 19 of the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*, provided that certain conditions are met:

- No individual should have to suffer for their opinions;
- Everyone has the right to freedom of expression; this right includes freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas of all kinds, whether orally, written or printed, or through any media of their choice.

The exercise of the aforementioned freedoms provided for in paragraph 2 of this article entails certain specific obligations and responsibilities and therefore this freedom may be subject to certain limits laid down by law, such that:

- the rights and reputations of others are respected;
- national security, public order, health and public morality are respected.

Another set of restrictions in the *International Covenant* refers to the prohibition by law of any war propaganda, any attempt to incite discrimination, violence and hostility on national, religious and racial grounds. An ample space is devoted to these limitations on the right to freedom of expression in the *International Convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination*, which was adopted by the *UN General Assembly* in Resolution 2106/XX of 21 December 1965.

On the basis of the provisions of the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*, the Council of Europe has established a considerable body of legislation, case law and certain standards concerning freedom of the press and access to information, so that these rights may be subject to certain formalities, restrictions, conditions or sanctions, in accordance with the law, in order to protect certain public and private interests.⁵

Returning strictly to the term *public relations*, it is a 20th century phenomenon with roots deep in history, promoting the practice of a wide range of strategies for socially influencing individuals, groups and other organisations. Although rigorous, the deontology of social and interpersonal relations is very complex, and such desiderata as: *do not lie*, *do not be lied to*, *do not manipulate* and *do not be manipulated* are paramount in this field.

These desiderata are constantly making their presence felt in the actions of public relations specialists, and ethical and legal guidance, in the context of the expansion of public relations, has become an imperative, which is also visible in the trend and, by implication, the effort to articulate a code of ethics for public relations.

⁵ Ibidem, pag 94

The primary links between organisations and public life are highlighted through a systemic approach to public relations, and it is of paramount importance that both organisations and public life as a whole include different human individuals with rights that are claimed to be legally established and of course practised. In other words, this is a fundamental feature of the democratic organisation of the rule of law.

The roots of the imperative of legality in the action of public relations specialists are to be found in the constitutional basis of the entire social organism, and according to the new Constitution of Romania, adopted on 8 December 1991, *the right of the individual to have access to any information of public interest cannot be restricted.*

At the same time, several obligations are laid down for *public authorities*, which have a duty to ensure that citizens are properly informed about political actions and issues of personal interest. We could therefore conclude that the right to information is a human necessity and implies *the freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas of all kinds, regardless of frontiers, in oral, written, printed or artistic form or by any other means of one's choice.*

Freedom of communication is the third of the freedoms and derives from the provisions mentioned in Articles 30, para. 3 and 31 para. 5 of the Constitution and states that *freedom of the press also implies the freedom to establish publications and public services (...), must guarantee the exercise of the right to broadcast to important social and political groups.*

The activities of public relations specialists involve a multitude of legal issues, as evidenced by the high number of civil and criminal cases in which they are involved on grounds of slander, offence, insult, etc. The criminal law firmly defends human honour and dignity, and every citizen has the right to respect for his or her integrity and right to privacy⁶.

If we ask ourselves how these acts are sanctioned by the criminal law, we will find that one of the offences against dignity is *insult* (Criminal Code, art. 205) by which the reputation and honour of an individual is tarnished. This tarnishing of honour can be carried out by words, in writing, and therefore implicitly in the written press, or by other means of expression. Free expression in the press, and in general, is therefore accompanied by a series of legal responsibilities which, if not respected, can lead to unpleasant consequences.

Conclusion

Our intention was to demonstrate that, in order to perform in the field of public relations, it is important for the journalist to have communication skills and competence in dealing with mass media methods, as well as a thorough knowledge of communication techniques with the general public, the principles of persuasion and, last but not least, the dynamics of public opinion.

⁶ Balahur, Doina, Gheorghe Teodorescu, Gheorghe-Ilie Fârte, Stefania Bejan, *Comunicare socială și relații publice*, Iași: Editura Universității "Alexandru Ioan Cuza", 2006, pages 125-129

REFERENCES

- Coman, C. (2000), *Relațiile publice și mass-media*, Iași, Polirom.
- Newsom, D. Carrell, B. (2004), *Redactarea materialelor de relații publice*, Iași, Polirom.
- Johnston, J. Zawawi, C. (2000), *Public Relations. Theory and Practice*, London, eBook Published.
- Săvulescu Matei, A. Munteanu, C. (2004), *Etică și deontologie în mass-media și relații publice*, Pitești, Independența Economică.
- Pop, D. (2000), *Introducere în teoria relațiilor publice*, Cluj-Napoca, Dacia.
- Runcan, M. (2002), *A patra putere – legislație și etică pentru jurnaliști*, Cluj-Napoca, Dacia.